

INTEGRATION OF SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY WIRES IN FIBER REINFORCED POLYMERS FOR ENDLESS CRASH ABSORBER STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Today most crash absorber elements are made of metals. Those materials absorb the energy during a crash event by ductile plastification. Fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) offer because of their heterogenic structure multiple failure mechanisms for energy absorption under compressive load. The low density leads to significant better specific energy absorption of FRP absorbers (50 J/g to 200 J/g FRP, 20 J/g steel, 40 J/g aluminum). However under tensile load fiber reinforced polymers show a brittle behavior and the energy absorption level is comparatively low. As a consequence of rising energy costs FRP with their good specific mechanical properties are used more and more for crash relevant structures in automobiles and aircrafts. For these applications high energy absorption and suppressed material separation is required under tensile load especially. The integration of ductile metal elements in FRP structures offers the possibility to improve the tensile crash behavior of fiber reinforced polymers significantly as the metal elements can prevent an early structure separation. The integration of shape memory alloys (SMA) with their pseudoplastic martensitic detwinning plateau enables the manufacturing of an “endless” crash absorber under tensile load. The detwinning stress plateau and the subsequent strain hardening are the key features of SMA material for this concept. Doing so, the SMA reinforced FRP is able to show a huge number of breaks in the FRP before a total failure of even the SMA takes place.

In this contribution we present a theoretical extrapolation of the behavior of these new hybrid structures under tensile loading, give an estimation of their potential and demonstrate a first experimental validation of this new concept.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the course of rising energy costs, lightweight construction is currently experiencing a rapid spread. FRP enter into more and more applications, such as automotive, sports and recreation [1]. But even in commercial aviation, in which they are already used for a long time, with the new models (Boeing 787 and Airbus A350), a new peak with a share of over 50% FRP in the structural mass is reached [2]. It is expected that the amount of fiber reinforced composites used for technical applications will be quadrupled until 2020 [3]. FRP offer due to their low density, good mechanical properties as well as their capability for function integration a high potential for lightweight design. So they are often superior to conventional metallic materials. For these reasons, they are used more and more for automotive applications, in aviation and space technology as well as in the recent past in areas of traditional mechanical and civil engineering. Especially in applications where weight reduction, increase of stiffness and strength, improvement of the long-term behavior and the comprehensive improvement of the performance of complex mechanisms are required, FRP show a highly efficient performance with their outstanding specific mechanical characteristics and the possibility to tailor them for many different applications [4,5].

FRP particularly with endless fiber reinforcement offer not only an excellent lightweight potential but also excellent energy absorption. If FRP structures are charged in compression to failure, extremely high amounts of energy absorption can be achieved beyond 100 J/g [6]. In many studies the

superiority of FRP to other materials such as metals for crushing-tests is documented [7,8]. This is a reason for the use of FRP in airplane and helicopter structures and in the future even more in automotive manufacture for energy absorbing structures. This high energy absorption is achieved by a large number of different failure mechanisms in FRP structures, as e.g. fiber-break, matrix-break, delamination, fiber pull-out, fiber-matrix-interphase failure and friction processes [9]. Another advantage is the progressive and stable progress of the crash front.

Figure 1: Material behavior of classical fiber reinforced composites and metal

Under tensile loading the situation is in terms of energy absorption radically different. In this case only the elastic strain to fiber breakage of the material can be used. On the material level Fig. 1 shows schematically the possible energy absorption capacity of FRP and metals under tensile and compression load. While under compression load significantly more energy can be absorbed by FRP than by metals it is for tensile load exactly the reverse. Metals have the possibility to plasticize, whereby they achieve higher elongation at break and with this absorb more energy. This disadvantage of FRP under tensile load often leads to separation of components by disintegration during a crash event, so that FRP cannot be used despite the otherwise excellent properties for the component.

In [10,11] an approach is shown to compensate this drawback of FRP under tensile loading by integrating steel fibers or rather a steel grid into the FRP structure. The steel reinforcement leads to a higher strength of the structure. The reinforcement is also able to prevent a separation of the structure until the maximum strain of the steel in the local field of strain is reached. After this the whole specimen suffers a catastrophic failure. Thus the integration of a steel grid leads to higher energy absorption of the structure and to a better failure mechanism. But nevertheless the energy absorption of the steel reinforced LFT is only a little bit higher than for single LFT because of the low strain

hardening of the steel grid, which limits the failure mechanism of the steel reinforced LFT to a single crack.

2 NEW APPROACH

In this contribution we present a new approach for the reinforcement of LFT for initiating a cascading effect and also reaching a higher energy absorption. Shape memory alloys, in our case NiTi, with their pseudoplastic detwinning plateau with a high increase of strain at a nearly constant stress level and their high strain hardening are predestined for this application. These characteristics of the reinforcement material of LFT enable a cascading effect of the specimens under tensile load. Fig. 2 shows the stress-strain behavior of SMA wires “Alloy M” from Memry GmbH.

Figure 2: Stress-strain behavior of SMA (Alloy M, Memry GmbH)

Figure 3: Theoretical force-deformation behavior of SMA-reinforced LFT (20 vol-%)

Fig. 3 reveals the results of theoretical calculation of the force-deformation behavior of SMA-reinforced LFT with 20 vol-% glass fiber content based on the sample geometries described in the experimental part. The graph in Fig. 3 demonstrates that a reinforcement of LFT with SMA can initiate a cascading effect in the specimen and with this an increase of about 30% of the energy absorption is possible.

For the integration of the reinforcing SMA SMA-grids are used. The wires orientated in direction of the tensile load (longitudinal wires) will prevent the separation of the LFT by the high strain hardening of SMA and also with this initiate the cascading effect of the absorber. However the cross wires of the grid have three main tasks. They provide the load transmission between SMA-grid and

LFT, serve as trigger mechanism to initiate failures by locally weakening the LFT and also they ensure a good handling of the reinforcing SMA elements as described in [12].

For a well-designed structure after a break of the LFT and the drop of the force level the SMA is deforming pseudoplastically while bearing the force of the whole structure. During strain hardening the force level raises again until another LFT break is initiated. For this concept a structure with defined ratio of LFT and SMA section shares is required. Properly designed, the absorbed energy under tensile load is significantly increased by synergetic effects of the multiple FRP failure and the plastic deformation of SMA.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Sample preparation

At first SMA-grids were spot welded for the sample preparation. Therefore the cross wires were spot welded to the longitudinal wires with a spacing of 8 mm. For the longitudinal wires as well as for the cross wires SMA wire, type Alloy M from Memry GmbH, with a diameter of 0.7 mm was used.

Figure 4: Sample for tensile tests

The SMA-grids were embedded in the LFT using a laboratory-hot-press from Dr. Collin GmbH. For sample preparation a stack consisting of a LFT layer, the SMA-grid and a second LFT layer was heated in the press up to 215 °C for 150 seconds without compression. The heated samples were afterwards consolidated with a pressure of 74 bar for 300 seconds and cooled down under pressure with 20 K per minute to 40 °C. The consolidated samples (thickness of 1.85 mm) were cut to a length of 180 mm and a width of 7.8 mm.

3.2 Sample testing

For mechanical tests a standard tensile testing machine (ZWICK1485) was used. The samples were fixed with hydraulic clamps with a clamping pressure of 150 bar. The samples were loaded to failure with a strain speed of 7.5 mm per minute.

4 RESULTS

Fig. 5 shows the failure sequence of a SMA-LFT specimen during quasi-static tensile testing. The cascading effect is clearly observable. The LFT breaks at t_2 in the middle of the specimen. After this the SMA wires are strained until the strain hardening leads to a stress level that is high enough, to initiate the next failure in the LFT (t_3). The third break occurs in the clamping area (t_4). Than two more breaks are initiated in the middle of the specimen (t_5 & t_6). In the tested specimen the longitudinal wires failed after the 5th break of the LFT (t_7).

Fig. 6 shows the force-deformation behavior of the tested sample. The diagram illustrates that all LFT failures occur at a force level of about 400 N. After the break of the LFT the force drops immediately. Only after the second break a slow decline of the force is visible. Fig. 5 shows that the emerging gap between the LFT-sections of this failure is much bigger than for the other failures.

Figure 5: Failure sequence of SMA-LFT during quasi-static tensile test

A comparison between Fig. 3 and Fig. 6 shows that the theoretical failure behavior of the SMA-reinforced LFT is nearly reached within the tests. Only the force level, which is required, to introduce a failure of the LFT is about 100 N lower in real tests than for the theoretical extrapolation.

Figure 6: Force-deformation behavior of SMA-reinforced LFT (20 vol-%)

5 CONCLUSION

The results lead to three important statements:

- A SMA-reinforcement of LFT is able to initiate a cascading effect during tensile testing and also prevents the separation of the structure.
- The SMA-reinforcement increases the energy absorption of LFT in first tests by about 20 % in comparison with the not-joined materials as shown in Fig. 7 (specific energy absorption of: SMA-LFT: 1,88 J/g, SMA: 0,86 J/g, LFT: 0,72 J/g). This shows that synergy effects lead to a improved failure behavior of LFT.
- A theoretical extrapolation (see Fig. 8) shows that specific energy absorption of 4 J/g will be possible if the design parameters of the structure (glass fiber content, SMA content, welding spots of SMA grid) are optimized.

Figure 7: Force-deformation behavior and specific absorbed energy of LFT, SMA and reinforced LFT

Further tests will be carried out to investigate the failure behavior of different strain rates as well as different specimen geometries. An optimization process based on experimental tests in combination with modeling and simulation will enable to figure out robust configurations, which show a higher energy absorption than reached with test samples in this contribution.

Figure 8: Theoretical force-deformation behavior of SMA-reinforced LFT

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